

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II), Rhodium(III) and Ruthenium(III) with Monobenzoylthiourea

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Monobenzoylthiourea is recommended as a complex forming reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II), rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III). The reagent forms a light yellow complex with palladium(II) in hydrochloric acid and a yellow complex with both rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) in the hot acetate medium. Palladium-monobenzoylthiourea complex is quantitatively extracted from 0.25N-8.0N hydrochloric acid medium with chloroform. Rhodium- and ruthenium-monobenzoylthiourea complexes are extracted with chloroform at pH 4.4-5.6 and pH 4.0-6.4 respectively. A large number of non-platinum metals do not interfere with the determination of the metal ions. Amongst the platinum metals, none interferes with the determination of palladium(II). Rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) are separately determined with the reagent by prior extraction of palladium(II). Gold(III) and iridium(III) do not interfere with the determination of rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III), but osmium(VI) and platinum(IV) interfere.

THIOUREA and several substituted thioureas¹⁻⁶ have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of platinum metals, but only a few of them are suitable for the determination of the metals in traces and in presence of foreign ions. In the present investigation monobenzoylthiourea is introduced as a new analytical reagent for platinum metals and is employed for the photometric determination of palladium(II), rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III). The complexes formed by these metal ions with monobenzoylthiourea are insoluble in water but soluble in ethanol, chloroform, methylisobutylketone and other common organic solvents. The metal complexes are extracted in chloroform for their subsequent spectrophotometric determination. The reagent is found to be highly suitable for the determination of palladium(II), rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) in presence of almost all the base metals. The advantage of the use of monobenzoylthiourea as a spectrophotometric reagent for palladium(II) lies in the fact that the metal ion can be determined in presence of large excess of all the other noble metals, by extracting the metal complex with chloroform from 4N hydrochloric acid medium. The interference of palladium(II) in the determination of rhodium(III), and ruthenium(III) can be avoided by prior extraction of palladium with the reagent from 2N hydrochloric acid medium. Amongst the other noble metals, osmium(VI) and platinum(IV) interfere with the determination of rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III). Moreover, the method is sensitive and comparable to the other available methods.

Palladium(II) forms also a light brown precipitate with the reagent at pH 4.0-6.0, the chloroform

extract of which ($\epsilon = 5.4 \times 10^3$) shows maximum absorbance at 365 nm. However, the analytical property of the light yellow palladium complex extracted from strong hydrochloric acid medium has been studied in detail because of its higher molar absorptivity ($\epsilon = 1.27 \times 10^4$). Ruthenium(III) forms a non-extractable pink coloured soluble complex ($\epsilon = 2.3 \times 10^3$) with monobenzoylthiourea in 6N hydrochloric acid medium after heating for 30 min. on a water bath; this complex has an absorption maximum at 540 nm. The molar absorptivity of the ruthenium-monobenzoylthiourea complex ($\epsilon = 8.2 \times 10^3$) formed in weakly acid medium (pH 4.0-6.4) is higher and, therefore, extracted with chloroform for determination of the metal.

Experimental

Apparatus: A Carl-Zeiss Spectrophotometer, Model PMQ-II, with 1.0 cm quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements. A Cambridge (Bench Model) pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was employed for pH measurements.

Standard metal solutions: Palladium(II), rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) solutions were made by dissolving the corresponding chlorides in dilute hydrochloric acid. The metal contents of the solutions were determined by precipitating with thio-salicylamide⁷. Dilute solutions of the metals for spectrophotometric determination were prepared by proper dilution of the stock solutions.

All the platinum metal salts (A.R.) were supplied by J. Mathey (U.K.).

Diverse ion solutions: Solutions of diverse ions (0.01M) were prepared by dissolving the sulphates,

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chlorides, nitrates or acetates of the corresponding metals in distilled water. Dilute hydrochloric acid (4.0*N*) was added where required.

Preparation and properties of the reagent: Monobenzoylthiourea (m.p. 170°) was prepared⁸ by heating thiourea and benzoylchloride at 120° and recrystallising the product from ethanol. Monobenzoylthiourea is insoluble in water but soluble in ethanol, chloroform and other common organic solvents. It is stable in strong acid medium. The reagent forms coloured precipitates with the following metal ions: platinum(IV), palladium(II), rhodium(III), ruthenium(III, VI), osmium(VI), copper(II) and mercury (II). The metal complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in common organic solvents.

Reagent solution: A 0.01*M* reagent solution in ethanol was used for the spectrophotometric determination of the metal ions.

All the reagents and chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Determination of palladium(II): Procedure: Place a measured amount of palladium(II) solution into a 100 ml separatory funnel and make the solution 2–3*N* with respect to hydrochloric acid. Add 2–3 ml of 0.01*M* monobenzoylthiourea solution, shake well and allow to stand for 5 min. Add 5.0 ml of ethanol and extract the light yellow palladium complex formed three to four times with 5.0 ml portions of chloroform. The addition of ethanol is necessary to avoid any scum formation at the interphase and for smooth extraction of the complex. Dilute the combined extract to 25.0 ml with chloroform in a volumetric flask and measure the absorbance at 340 nm against a blank solution prepared under the same conditions with the same quantity of the reagent.

Determination of rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) separately: Procedure: Place a known amount of rhodium(III) or ruthenium(III) solution into a 100 ml separatory funnel and adjust to pH 4.5–5.5 with 1.0*M* hydrochloric acid and 10% sodium acetate solution. Add 2–3 ml of 0.01*M* reagent solution, mix thoroughly and place over a boiling water bath for about 20 min. Cool to room temperature, add 5.0 ml of ethanol and extract 2–3 times with 5.0 ml portions of chloroform. Dilute the combined extract to 25.0 ml with chloroform in a volumetric flask and measure the absorbance at 340 nm for rhodium and at 350 nm for ruthenium against an appropriate reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves: The absorbance curves of the solutions of the metal complexes determined by the above procedure are shown in Fig. 1. The chloroform extract of the palladium, rhodium and ruthenium complexes showed maximum absorption at 325 nm, 330 nm and 340 nm respectively. The reagent has practically no absorption at 340 nm and above.

Effect of pH: The acidity of the palladium(II), rhodium(III) or ruthenium(III) solution was adjusted by adding varying amounts of 10% sodium

acetate and hydrochloric acid. The acidity of the aqueous layer was measured after extraction of the metal complexes either by titrating against a standard alkali or with the aid of a pH meter. The optimum

Fig. 1 Absorbance Curves for Palladium, Rhodium and Ruthenium Complexes of Monobenzoylthiourea in chloroform.

- ⊙ Pd—complex (1.665 μg Pd/ml)
- Rh—complex (6.4 μg Ru/ml)
- △ Ru—complex (6.2 μg Ru/ml)
- Pd—complex extracted at pH 5.2 (5 μg Pd/ml)
- Reagent (10^{-3} *M*).

acidities for 100% extraction of the metal ions were as follows: Pd (0.25*N*–8.0*N* HCl), Rh (pH 4.4–5.6) and Ru (pH 4.0–6.4).

Stability of the colour: The colour of chloroform extracts of the metal complexes were found to be stable for 48 hr and then faded gradually.

Conformity to Beer's law: The absorbance of the palladium, ruthenium and rhodium complexes followed Beer's law at 340 nm, 350 nm and 340 nm over the concentration range of 1.6–6.7 μg , Pd ml⁻¹, 2.08–12.5 μg Ru ml⁻¹ and 2.4–9.6 μg Rh ml⁻¹ respectively.

Optimum concentration range: According to Sandell⁹ the most favourable range for making absorbance measurements is from 0.2 to 0.7 absorbance unit. The corresponding concentration ranges for the metal ions are given in Table 1.

Molar absorptivity, sensitivity, precision and accuracy: The molar absorptivities of the metal complexes, the sensitivity, coefficient of variation and relative mean error for the determinations are summarized in Table 1.

Nature of the complexes and effect of reagent concentration: The empirical formula for the palladium-monobenzoylthiourea and rhodium-monobenzoylthiourea complexes were determined by the molar ratio method¹⁰. The results indicate that monobenzoylthiourea forms a 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes with palladium and rhodium respectively. These ratios were verified by the slope ratio method.

The composition of ruthenium-monobenzoylthiourea complex could not be determined by any of the conventional methods. It has been found that for

TABLE 1—OPTIMUM CONCENTRATION RANGE, MOLAR ABSORPTIVITY, SENSITIVITY PRECISION AND ACCURACY

Complex	Optimum concentration range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Molar absorptivity	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	Co-efficient of variation (%)	Relative mean error (%)
Palladium-monobenzoylthiourea	1.8–6.3	1.27×10^4	0.00832	0.62	0.25
Rhodium-monobenzoylthiourea	2.7–9.5	7.7×10^3	0.01400	0.78	0.32
Ruthenium-monobenzoylthiourea	2.5–8.75	8.2×10^3	0.01227	0.82	0.33

complete extraction of ruthenium as monobenzoylthiourea complex, the molar concentration of the reagent must be 16 times greater than that of ruthenium(III). The high consumption of the

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE INDIVIDUAL DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM(II), RHODIUM(III) AND RUTHENIUM(III)

Palladium (87.4 μg)		Rhodium (120.0 μg)		Ruthenium (144.0 μg)	
Diverse ions	Amount tolerated (μg)	Diverse ions	Amount tolerated (μg)	Diverse ions	Amount tolerated (μg)
Co^{2+}	5.6×10^3	Co^{2+}	1000 ^b	Co^{2+}	1500 ^b
Ni^{2+}	33.5×10^3	Ni^{2+}	1000 ^b	Ni^{2+}	1800 ^b
Zn^{2+}	24.0×10^4	Mn^{2+}	800 ^b	Zn^{2+}	2000 ^b
Mn^{2+}	9.0×10^4	Zn^{2+}	1200 ^b	Mn^{2+}	1000 ^b
Cu^{2+}	2000	Cu^{2+}	150 ^c	Cu^{2+}	200 ^c
Fe^{3+}	2000 ^a	Fe^{3+}	200 ^b	Fe^{3+}	200 ^b
Cd^{2+}	3000	Cd^{2+}	800 ^b	Cd^{2+}	1500 ^b
Al^{3+}	3500	Al^{3+}	1000 ^b	Al^{3+}	1500 ^b
Ga^{3+}	4000	UO_2^{2+}	600	UO_2^{2+}	600
UO_2^{2+}	1000	Ti^{3+}	100 ^b	Ti^{3+}	100 ^b
Ti^{4+}	500	Mo^{6+}	1000 ^b	Mo^{6+}	1200 ^b
Ti^{3+}	500	W^{6+}	1500 ^b	W^{6+}	1200 ^b
Mo^{6+}	1500	Au^{3+}	100	Au^{3+}	100
W^{6+}	1500	Pd^{2+}	125	Pd^{2+}	125
Pt^{4+}	500	Ir^{3+}	200	Ir^{3+}	200
Rh^{3+}	300	Pt^{4+}	Interferes	Pt^{4+}	Interferes
Au^{3+}	200	Ru^{3+}	Interferes	Rh^{3+}	Interferes
Ru^{3+}	200	Os^{6+}	Interferes	Os^{6+}	Interferes
Ir^{3+}	200				
Os^{6+}	300				

a In presence of phosphate ions;

b In presence of tartrate ions;

c In presence of E.D.T.A.

reagent may be ascribed to the reduction of ruthenium(III) to the divalent state by the reagent before the formation of the complex. Moreover, a large amount of reagent may be required to suppress the dissociation of the ruthenium complex.

Dissociation constant of palladium and rhodium complexes: Dissociation constants of the palladium— and rhodium—monobenzoylthiourea complexes in chloroform were calculated from the molar ratio curves¹¹ and found to be 6.0×10^{-14} and 8.7×10^{-17} respectively.

Effect of diverse ions: Palladium(II), rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) were separately determined with monobenzoylthiourea in presence of known amounts of a large number of diverse ions, following the procedures described above. Palladium was determined in presence of a large excess of all the platinum metals and gold by extracting the metal complex from 4N hydrochloric acid medium. Rhodium or ruthenium was separately determined in presence of excess palladium by prior extraction of the latter at 2N hydrochloric acid as described above. Rhodium or ruthenium in aqueous layer was subsequently extracted by the use of the reagent at pH 4.6. Platinum(IV) and osmium(VI) interfered with the determination of both ruthenium and rhodium. The tolerance limits for various diverse ions (Table 2) represent the concentrations of foreign ions in presence of which the transmittance of the corresponding complex solution obtained was within $\pm 2\%$ of the expected value.

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